

IMPACT OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES ON GREEN CREATIVITY: MEDIATING ROLE OF EMPLOYEE GREEN COMMITMENT

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of circular economy practices on green creativity, mediated by employee green commitment, in the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. To test the proposed hypothesis, primary data were collected using a questionnaire adapted from previous studies. A total sample of 199 top management-level individuals was considered. The gathered data were tested in SmartPLS version 3 through structural equation modeling. Findings of this confirmed that all direct paths, such as circular economy practices, have a positive and significant impact on both green creativity and employee green commitment. Similarly, employee green commitment has a positive and significant impact on green creativity. Additionally, the partial mediation effect of employee green commitment on the relationship between circular economy practices and green creativity was also confirmed. Such findings indicate that although circular practices have a direct beneficial effect on environmental innovation, most of them work by enhancing employees' commitment to environmental sustainability. The practical implications also suggest that manufacturing companies should integrate circular economy practices and mitigation measures to encourage their workforce on the environmental front, such as participatory green programs and sustainability-based reward schemes. In the case of Pakistan, where the industrial sector generates most of the pollution, this dual strategy will provide the sector with a platform to achieve operational sustainability and a competitive edge simultaneously through eco-innovation. The paper will contribute to the sustainable business literature by providing empirical evidence to support the psychological processes that connect organizational practices and environmental creativity, particularly in the context of an emerging economy.

INTRODUCTION

The mounting environmental pollution and depletion of natural resources have underscored the

need for sustainable business practices worldwide (Aiguoabarueghian et al., 2024). Nevertheless,

industries, especially in developing countries such as Pakistan, face significant hurdles in implementing circular economy (CE) practices due to a lack of awareness, high costs, and insufficient energy to implement these practices. There is an overuse of resources and an overproduction of waste as manufacturing companies prioritize short-term profits over long-term economic benefits (Junejo et al., 2020). Additionally, although green creativity, as described as the generation of innovative and environmentally friendly ideas, is very important in the area of sustainability, most organizations find it challenging to cultivate it due to their rigid organizational structures and the limited involvement of employees in environmental campaigns. It is on these challenges that there is a need to examine how CE practice can be effectively utilized in promoting green creativity, especially by leveraging employee commitment (Mansoor et al., 2021).

The principles of the circular economy include waste minimization, material reuse, and restoration, thereby displacing the conventional linear model of 'take-make-waste' production with a closed-loop approach (Duc & Dinh, 2024). Such practices are not only environmentally friendly but also processes that bring innovation in products, processes, and business models (Junejo et al., 2020). In this case, green creativity is elicited through organizations that apply CE principles in their business operations, allowing employees to develop sustainable solutions. Nonetheless, merely adopting the practice of CE does not necessarily lead to creative achievements unless workers are encouraged to participate in environmental objectives. The question then is how organizations can convert their CE strategies into actionable and innovative green ideas.

Employee green commitment, as a psychological attachment and commitment to environmental sustainability, serves as the key mediating factor in the relationship between CE practices and green creativity (Sohu et al., 2022). Employees who are morally and emotionally invested in sustainability are more likely to engage in proactive solutions to problems that arise than their counterparts when firms undertake CE initiatives to develop eco-innovative ideas (Farooq et al., 2021). Their dedication becomes the pincer that relieves organizations of sustainability policies and directs them toward individual creative endeavors.

The role of top management is also significant because, if they support employee motivation for green commitment through their leadership in the use of CE, then a culture of green creativity can be created (Idrees et al., 2022).

The rationale for conducting this research is that it is crucial to enhance sustainable industrial practices in Pakistan's manufacturing industry, which is a significant contributor to economic growth but also contributes to environmental pollution (Kumar et al., 2023). The ecological and competitive benefits can be realized by understanding how employees' commitment to CE practices acts as a catalyst for green creativity. In addition, top management is a decisive stakeholder in policy crafting; therefore, their insights are crucial in determining the viability of the CE strategy.

Although a growing body of literature has been generated on the subject of CE and green creativity, little research has focused on the moderating effects of employee green commitment, especially in emerging economies such as Pakistan. This study addresses this gap by examining the impacts of CE practices on green creativity in the context of employee commitment, targeting top management respondents in the manufacturing industry. In this way, it can add value to the literature by providing empirical evidence of the psychological processes underlying the correlation between organizational sustainability practices and innovative outcomes. It also has practical implications for policymakers and business leaders who wish to promote a greener economy.

Literature review

Circular Economy Practices

The transition from a linear economy to a circular economy supports the sustainable use of resources by minimizing waste and maximizing efficiency (Sharma et al., 2021). Practices such as recycling, remanufacturing, and eco-friendly product designs, which are integral to the circular economy, urge companies to be creative in their procedures that minimize environmental destruction. Such practices establish a company culture that encourages green innovation, the invention of novel, ecologically friendly ideas and solutions. Companies that adopt circular concepts challenge their employees to take a

new perspective, which leads to innovative solutions in production, waste management, and even the maximization of product life (Mostaghimi & Behnamian, 2023). There is also research to support the fact that companies implementing circular economy strategies feel more creative in terms of green innovation, as employees are constantly being challenged to discard old ways and seek more sustainable solutions.

Green commitment among employees refers to a person's willingness to maintain a healthy workplace environment (Faezah et al., 2024). When organizations adopt circular economy practices, it sends a clear message about their level of commitment to sustainability, which in turn translates to a change in the attitude and behavior of employees. Workers in this culture form a stronger emotional and ethical bond towards environmentally friendly programs because they perceive their company as working to minimize waste and ensure the efficient use of resources (Usman et al., 2023). A match between organizational values and personal beliefs about the environment enhances employees' green commitment. Research has shown that the higher the level of circular activities within a company, the stronger the force is on the employee side to achieve sustainability aims, which makes employees more determined to stick to the green side over the long term (Li et al., 2023).

H1: Circular economy practices have positive and significant impact on green creativity

H2: Circular economy practices have positive and significant impact on employee green commitment

Mediating role of Employee Green Commitment

Those employees who strongly believe in environmental sustainability tend to participate in creative problem-solving to promote the goals of a green environment (Zafar et al., 2025). A green commitment encourages people not to stay on the usual track of operations, but to find new approaches to enhance the sustainability of the working process (Sohu et al., 2024). These staff members will self-initiate ideas on how to go green, experiment with green materials, and utilize resources to their maximum potential (Sarkar, 2025). They tend to become crucial participants in green creativity due to their desire and concern for the environment (Junejo

et al., 2022). It is empirically believed that more committed green employees contribute to a higher level of innovation in sustainability-driven projects within organizations, as such employees are more likely to invest their efforts in designing and introducing new, environmentally friendly solutions. The connection between the practices of circular economy and green creativity is not direct, but rather strongly contingent upon employee green commitment. Although the circular practices present a framework for sustainability, the efforts of employees make these practices a reality by putting them into practice through innovation (Singh et al., 2025). Employees who are committed to environmental goals also serve as catalysts, ensuring that circularity strategies yield practical innovations of a specific kind. Their involvement is situated between policy implementation on one end and creative execution on the other, and they play a key middle role in this association. The studies demonstrate that organizations with well-developed circular economy policies have achieved higher levels of green creativity when employees are emotionally and psychologically invested in sustainability. Therefore, it is essential to encourage employees' green commitment to make the most of novel approaches to cyclical economy projects (Haque et al., 2024).

H3: Employee green commitment has positive and significant impact on green creativity.

H4: Employee green commitment mediates the relationship between circular economy practices and green creativity.

Methodology

In this research, a quantitative research design will be employed to investigate the relationship between the practice of a circular economy and employee green commitment and green creativity in Pakistan's manufacturing industry. The study is based on primary data gathered through a face-to-face survey procedure using a modified questionnaire, which was adapted from existing measurement scales. The survey instrument used will cover three primary constructs: practices of the circular economy, employee green commitment, and green creativity, on a 5-point Likert rating scale with response options ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The target group consists of top management professionals

(managers, directors, and CEOs) from manufacturing companies in Pakistan, comprising 199 respondents. These respondents will be selected using convenience sampling, as it is the most suitable method due to its ease of access and convenience (Golzar et al., 2022). The face-to-face approach was adopted because it was considered that this method would yield high response rates and transparency of responses, which was necessary. At the same time, the anonymity of all participant information would not be compromised. Reliability tests were employed in the data analysis to assess the consistency of measurement, and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses (Hajjar, 2018). Mediation analysis has received special attention to estimate the relationship between employee green commitment and the effect of circular economy practices on green creativity. The study adheres to the ethical requirements of research, ensuring that participation is voluntary, informed consent is obtained, and the identities of respondents remain fully anonymous. This methodology provides an effective means of evaluating the complex relationships between organizational sustainability practices and the environmental innovations performed by employees in the industrial context of Pakistan.

Results and Discussion

Reliability and validity

The outcome demonstrates a supportive effect of the reliability and validity of all three constructs in the

study, including circular economy practices (CEP), employee green commitment (EGC), and green creativity (GC).

Internal consistency reliability is also high in all constructs, as the Cronbach's alpha values are significantly higher than the recommended threshold of 0.7 (CEP: 0.89, EGC: 0.93, GC: 0.90). The reliability of measurement scales is also high with a score scale of 0.92 to 0.94 (composite reliability). Individual constructs also appear to have good convergent validity, with all item loadings above 0.7 (0.745 to 0.902) and the average variance extracted (AVE) above 0.5 (CEP = 0.657, EGC = 0.687, GC = 0.714).

The specific high scores of employee green commitment (having the most significant reliability coefficients) indicate the possibility that this scale is highly accurate in measuring the construct. All the constructs can be deemed equal in terms of validity requirements, and circular economy practices falls slightly short (but still acceptable) in AVE values relative to the rest. The unity of factor loading among all items indicates that all the question items are quite adequate in assessing the latent variable to which they belong. These statistics support the fact that the measurement model is both reliable and valid, enabling the determination of the hypothesized relationships in the research. (See Table 1)

Table 1. Reliability and validity

Variable	Item coding	Item loading	Cronbach alpha value	Composite reliability	Average variance extraction
Circular Economy Practices	CEP1	0.817	0.896	0.920	0.657
	CEP2	0.806			
	CEP3	0.811			
	CEP4	0.819			
	CEP5	0.818			
	CEP6	0.792			
Employee green commitment	EGC1	0.840	0.935	0.946	0.687
	EGC2	0.822			
	EGC3	0.827			
	EGC4	0.882			
	EGC5	0.842			
	EGC6	0.745			
	EGC7	0.831			
	EGC8	0.835			

Green Creativity	GC1	0.902	0.900	0.926	0.714
	GC2	0.810			
	GC3	0.818			
	GC4	0.868			
	GC5	0.825			

Path Directions

The findings of the path analysis provide a solid empirical foundation for all the proposed relations in the study. The direct impacts demonstrate that all primary constructs include statistically significant relations with each other: circular economy practices (CEP) have a substantial positive effect on green creativity (BC 0.401, $t = 6.555$) and employee green commitment (EGC) and employee green commitment (EGC) has a significant effect on green creativity (BC 0.436, $t = 6.957$). The t -value is significantly above the calibrated value of 1.96 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that these relations are highly significant.

The mediation analysis indicates that employee green commitment has a partial mediating effect in the relationship between circular economy practices and green creativity, as the indirect effect is significant

(0.315, $t = 6.445$). This partial mediation suggests that the direct impact of CEP on green creativity may be perceived as minor. In contrast, a significant portion of it (approximately 44% of the total effect) is driven by the increase in employees' environmental commitment. The high values of beta between the modules, especially those of the CEP->EGC path (0.722), indicate that embracing the circular economy is highly effective in enhancing employees' commitment to the concept of sustainability, which ultimately proves to be a significant generator of eco-innovation strength within the organization. These strong results indicate that the theoretical framework receives ample support from the empirical data presented, and that employee commitment fosters an understanding of how sustainable business practices can be leveraged to create innovative environmental solutions. (See Table 1 and Figure 1)

Table 2. Path Directions

Path Direction (Direct effects)	Beta value	T-value	Remarks
Circular Economy Practices -> Green Creativity	0.401	6.555	Supported
Circular Economy Practices -> Employee Green Commitment	0.722	23.019	Supported
Employee Green Commitment -> Green Creativity	0.436	6.957	Supported
Path Direction (Indirect effects)	Beta value	T-value	Remarks
Circular Economy Practices -> Employee Green Commitment -> Green Creativity	0.315	6.445	Partially mediation effect

Figure 1. SEM

Discussion and practical implications

The results of the present investigation help to understand better how the circular economic behavior influences green creativity among manufacturing companies, with employee green commitment serving as the essential intermediary factor. The existence of such a highly positive correlation between circular economy practices and green creativity suggests that when a company adopts sustainable strategies, such as waste reduction, recycling, and eco-design, the process fosters the immediate development of innovative environmental solutions (AbdelKader, 2023). This is consistent with the rising awareness of the inherent potential of circular business models to facilitate creative thinking, as these models disrupt the linear way of doing business and make resource optimization the new normal (Hongyun et al., 2025).

The extremely high influence of circular economy habits on employee commitment (0.722) indicates that when companies adopt sustainable operations, it has a significant impact on employees, encouraging them to focus their efforts on reducing the negative environmental impact. This intuitively follows; employees deduce that their organization is serious about sustainability and is making progress towards achieving its goals because they are aware of the practical efforts being undertaken in this direction (Roša et al., 2025). The fact that such commitment is significantly related to green creativity ($r = 0.436$) underlines the importance of employee buy-in in transforming organizational statements into reality in the form of green creativity (Shah et al., 2021).

Of special practical value is the mediation analysis. The partial mediation effect ($\beta = 0.315$) indicates that, although circular practices directly enhance creativity, nearly half of their positive influence is mediated through increased workers' commitment to the environment. This indicates that organizations should not only engage in circular economy activities, but also work towards developing genuine employee engagement with sustainability objectives as definitive strategies to achieve creative potential within the organization (Kherazi et al., 2024).

These results are particularly applicable in the case of Pakistan's manufacturing industry, where a peculiar difficulty remains in adopting sustainability. These findings demonstrate that top management can

spearhead environmental innovation through a two-pronged strategy: engaging in practice-based circular economy activities on the one hand, and fostering an emotional attachment to sustainability among employees on the other.

Theoretically, the study extends our knowledge and understanding of the psychological processes that associate organizational sustainability practices with the resultant innovative consequences. It is more accurate to explain how the circular economy-green creativity relationship occurs, given the possibility of empirically demonstrating the role of employee commitment as a mediator in the process of turning environmental initiatives into concrete outcomes. The powerful impact of circular practices on employee commitment also reveals that a clear commitment towards sustainability might be more effective at fostering environmental commitment compared to policies and mission statements.

These results convey a message to practitioners that they should not only consider adopting the circular economy as an operational change, but also as a cultural one. Technical circular solutions should be accompanied by efforts to emotionally engage employees in the sustainability targets of companies that aim to enhance their green creativity. These may involve including people in the decision-making process of circular strategies, recognizing rewards for green ideas, and promoting open communication about environmental consequences.

Focusing the study on respondents in top management adds a level of significance to the mentioned criteria, as it implies that the example of circular practices introduced by top management causes a ripple effect across the organization. It appears that having executives promote sustainability by demonstrating real initiatives has significant implications for both the dedication of the middle management team and the organization's overall innovative ability in addressing environmental issues. These results are excellent; however, it is worth noting that this research is based on the Pakistani manufacturing industry, and the results may differ in other cultural or industrial environments. The partial mediation effect also opens an avenue for exploring other potential mediators or moderators that can further explain the relationship between the circular economy and green creativity.

Conclusion

The study presents a compelling argument that incorporating a circular economy and promoting employee green commitment can be mutually supportive options in fostering environmental innovation. The findings suggest that the most effective organizations in the context of sustainability should be those that successfully integrate both operational and staff-oriented changes in a mutually beneficial cycle, where business and employee values support one another to create innovative green solutions. Such an all-inclusive strategy could potentially provide a solution for sustainable manufacturing firms in emerging economies, such as Pakistan, to gain an environmental and market advantage in the current globally changing marketplace, which is becoming increasingly sustainability-driven.

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